

TALABALARNING KASBIY KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETENSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KORPUS TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI

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Anotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada talabalarning kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda korpus ta'lim texnologiyalarining lingvodidaktik imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Korpusga asoslangan yondashuvning pedagogik mohiyati autentik til materiallari asosida o'qitish, til birliklarining real qo'llanilishini empirik tahlil qilish va faol muloqotga yo'naltirilgan o'quv muhitini yaratish imkoniyati bilan asoslanadi. Tadqiqotda milliy va xorijiy tilshunos olimlarning korpus haqidagi nazariy qarashlari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi hamda korpus lingvistikasining tarixiy taraqqiyot bosqichlari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Data-Driven Learning (DDL) konsepsiyasi, registr va diskurs tahlili asosida korpus texnologiyalarining nofilologik yo'nalish talabalari uchun metodik samaradorligi ochib beriladi. Xulosa sifatida korpus yondashuvi talabaning analitik tafakkurini, mustaqil tadqiqot ko'nikmalarini va kasbiy nutqiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantiruvchi integrativ metodologiya ekanligi asoslanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: korpus lingvistikasi, korpus ta'lim texnologiyalari, kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiya, autentik material, DDL, registr, diskurs, lingvodidaktika, ESP.

Abstract. This article analyzes the linguodidactic potential of corpus-based educational technologies in developing students' professional communicative competence. The pedagogical significance of the corpus-based approach is justified by its ability to provide authentic language input, enable empirical analysis of real language use, and create a communication-oriented learning environment. The study comparatively examines national and international theoretical perspectives on corpus linguistics and outlines the historical development of corpus technologies. Particular attention is paid to the Data-Driven Learning (DDL) approach, register variation, and discourse analysis as effective methodological tools for non-philological (ESP) students. The findings demonstrate that corpus-based methodology serves not merely as a technical tool but as an integrative framework that enhances students' analytical thinking, research autonomy, and professional communicative competence.

Keywords: corpus linguistics, corpus-based education, professional communicative competence, authentic materials, data-driven learning, register analysis, discourse, ESP, linguodidactics.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются лингводидактические возможности корпусных образовательных технологий в развитии профессиональной коммуникативной компетенции студентов. Педагогическая значимость корпусного подхода обосновывается использованием аутентичных языковых материалов, эмпирическим анализом реального функционирования языковых единиц и созданием коммуникативно-ориентированной образовательной среды. Рассматриваются теоретические взгляды отечественных и зарубежных ученых на понятие корпуса, а также этапы развития

корпусной лингвистики. Особое внимание уделяется концепции *Data-Driven Learning (DDL)*, анализу регистров и дискурса как эффективным методическим инструментам для студентов нефилологических направлений (*ESP*). Делается вывод о том, что корпусный подход представляет собой не просто техническое средство, а интегративную методологию, способствующую развитию аналитического мышления, исследовательской самостоятельности и профессиональной коммуникативной компетенции студентов.

Ключевые слова: корпусная лингвистика, корпусные образовательные технологии, профессиональная коммуникативная компетенция, аутентичные материалы, *DDL*, регистр, дискурс, *ESP*, лингводидактика.

Talabalarining kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda korpus ta'lim texnologiyalarining o'rni beqiyosdir. Korpusga asoslangan yondashuvning pedagogik ahamiyati, avvalambor, til materialini autentik manbalar asosida o'rganish, til birliklarining voqeiy qo'llanilishini tahlil qilish, faol muloqotga yo'naltirilgan o'quv muhitini yaratish va o'quv jarayonida nutqiy-funksional yondashuvni amalga oshirish imkoniyati bilan izohlanadi [12; 14]. Mazkur yondashuv orqali ilmiy tadqiqotlarda “korpus ta'lim texnologiyalari” tushunchasining mazmun-mohiyati va uning lingvodidaktik imkoniyatlari aniqlandi. Korpus lingvistikasining taraqqiyoti natijasida ushbu tushuncha turli ilmiy maktablar va olimlar tomonidan o'ziga xos jihatlar bilan boyitib kelinmoqda [19; 4].

Xususan, milliy tilshunoslikda korpusga ko'proq lingvodidaktik va integrativ yondashuv obyekti sifatida qaraladi. Olima G.G. Rajabova ta'rifiga ko'ra, korpus — bu autentik til muhitining raqamli modeli bo'lib, u darsliklardagi sun'iylikni bartaraf etishga va talabalarni jonli professional muloqotga tayyorlashga xizmat qiluvchi empirik manbadir [24]. D.R. Pulatova esa korpusni nofilologik yo'nalish talabalarining kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda fundamental baza vazifasini o'taydigan, sohaviy terminologiya va diskursiv qoliplarni o'zida jamlagan tizimli-funksional birliklar to'plami sifatida tavsiflaydi [22; 23].

MDH olimlari tadqiqotlarida esa korpusni metodik va tizimli yondashuv asosida o'rganish ustuvorlik qiladi. Masalan, P.V. Sysoev korpusga talabalarining tahliliy va tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiluvchi didaktik axborot muhiti deb ta'rif beradi [30]. V.P. Zakharov esa korpusning texnik imkoniyatlariga urg'u berib, unga “informativ-izlov tizimi” sifatida yondashadi [31; 32]. Shu bilan birga, L.K. Raitskaya korpusni zamonaviy ta'limning kognitiv resursi deb ataydi va uning yordamida o'quvchi tilning yashirin qonuniyatlarini mustaqil ravishda “kashf etish” imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishini ta'kidlaydi [25; 26].

Xorijiy tilshunoslikda esa korpusga asosan reprezentativlik va empirik ma'lumotlar manbai sifatida qaraladi. John Sinclair korpusni tilning yoki uning bir qismining holatini aks ettirish uchun maxsus tanlab olingan matnlar majmuasi deb ta'riflaydi [28; 29]. Douglas Biber “lingvistik vakillik” tamoyiliga tayangan holda korpus dizaynining ilmiy asoslarini ishlab chiqqan [2; 3]. Tony McEnery va Andrew Hardie esa korpusning texnologik xususiyatini birinchi o'ringa qo'yib, unga kompyuterda qayta ishlanadigan va lingvistik markyorlar bilan boyitilgan tabiiy nutq namunalari to'plami sifatida ta'rif beradilar [19].

XX asrning oxirlarida axborotlashtirish jarayonining jadallashuvi va kompyuter texnologiyalarining ta'lim tizimiga kirib kelishi ilk elektron korpuslarning yaratilishiga xizmat qildi [13; 18]. Ushbu elektron korpuslar turli janrlardagi yozma va og'zaki matnlarning yirik

to‘plamlaridan iborat bo‘lib, tilni lingvistik jihatdan har tomonlama tahlil qilishda yangi ufqlarni ochdi [10].

Dastlabki korpuslarning miqyos jihatdan kengayishi natijasida lisoniy faktlarni shunchaki to‘plashdan ularni chuqur strukturaviy tahlil qilish bosqichiga o‘tildi hamda izohli (annotated) korpuslar shakllandi [15]. Bunday korpuslarda matnning grammatik va semantik belgilari elektron tarzda tizimlashtirildi [4].

Ayniqsa, xorijiy til korpuslarida materiallarni tayyorlash va belgilash jarayonlarining takomillashuvi korpus texnologiyalarining ta‘limdagi amaliy qiymatini oshirdi [1; 9].

Korpusga asoslangan ta‘lim yondashuvi talabalarda faol muloqotga yo‘naltirilgan o‘quv muhitini yaratadi, chunki unda autentik materiallar real kasbiy vaziyatlardagi nutqiy birliklarni tahlil qilish uchun asos bo‘lib xizmat qiladi [14]. McEnery va Wilson ta‘kidlashicha, korpus yondashuvi tilni intuitiv taxminlar asosida emas, balki real faktlar va statistik ma‘lumotlar asosida o‘rganishni taqozo etadi [20; 21]. Sinclair esa kollokatsiya tamoyiliga urg‘u berib, tilning kontekstual birliklar asosida tashkil topishini ko‘rsatadi [28].

Tim Johns Data-Driven Learning (DDL) konsepsiyasini ilgari surib, talabaning mustaqil tahlil va xulosa chiqarish jarayonini asoslaydi [16]. D. Biber va G. Kennedy korpuslarning turli registrlarga ajratilishini ilmiy jihatdan izohlab, ESP yo‘nalishida ularning samaradorligini ko‘rsatib berganlar [3; 17].

P.V. Sysoev va U. Römer korpus texnologiyalarini o‘qituvchi uchun autentik materiallar manbai, talaba uchun esa reflektiv baholash vositasi sifatida baholaydilar [30; 27].

Demak, korpus yondashuvi shunchaki texnik vosita emas, balki talabaning kasbiy kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantiruvchi integrativ metodologiyadir [12; 19].

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